

**Effect of Heat treatment and Ni-P coating for SiC particulate
on Mechanical behaviors of SiC_p/2024 Al Alloy Composites**

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ABSTRACT

In this paper, the effect of Ni-P coating for SiC particle and heat treatment in SiC_p/2024 Al composites has been studied in relation with mechanical properties. After Ni-P coating for SiC particles, both the tensile strength and elongation in Ni-P coated SiC particle reinforced composites were found to be decreased in comparison with uncoated SiC particle reinforced composites. This is due to the formation of brittle and hard Ni₃P in Ni-P coating layer during fabrication process at 520°C consolidation temperature. After heat treatment, the specific strength of the composites was remarkably increased and the specific modulus of SiC_p/2024 Al composites was lineally increased as the volume fraction of SiC particles increases. Therefore, the specific modulus and the specific strength of SiC_p/2024 Al composites were greatly influenced by volume fraction of SiC particles and properties of 2024 Al matrix, respectively.

Keywords : SiC particulate, Al matrix composites, heat treatment, elastic property, specific modulus, specific strength, vacuum hot pressing

1. INTRODUCTION

Aluminum alloys reinforced with whisker or particulate SiC are attractive for applications requiring higher stiffness, strength and resistance to wear than traditional aluminum alloys.[1-5] These composites are particularly advantageous because these can be fabricated by conventional metal-working techniques such as extrusion, forging, and rolling.[1,6] One of the major factors in composites strengthening is that the load is effectively transferred from the matrix to the reinforcement. In order to obtain the best properties in the composites, the compatibility was required physically and chemically

between the reinforcing whisker (or particles) and matrix alloys. Therefore, in the case of continuous fiber reinforced composites, much work has been done for the effect of reinforcement modification such as surface coating and surface treatment, and improvement of matrix composition.[7,8] However, there is a little published data describing coating effect on discontinuous fiber reinforced composites. In our previous study[9], we could obtain excellent mechanical properties by Ni-P coating for whisker in $K_2O \cdot 6TiO_2$ /Al composites made by hot-pressing in an argon atmosphere. These results showed that bonding between $K_2O \cdot 6TiO_2$ whisker and Al matrix was improved by the Ni-P on whisker. In the case of discontinuous fiber reinforced Al composites, the role of aging hardenable Al alloy matrix has not been emphasized in previous papers on the strength of Al MMC's[1-6].

Therefore, the purpose of this study is to investigate for the influence of Ni-P coating on SiC particles by means of interfacial control and the effect of heat treatment of matrix on tensile properties of SiCp/2024 Al composites.

2. EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURES

SiC particles, produced by Daiheiyu Co., with average size of $8\mu m$ were used for reinforcement. The Ni-P electroless plating thickness for SiC particle was $0.3\mu m$. Both coated and uncoated particles were mixed with 2024 Al powder in a sodium alginate solution with pH 9 by the use of an ultrasonic apparatus in order to avoid agglomeration of particles and then dried. The mixtures were degassed at $450^\circ C$ for 2 hours and then compacted by vacuum hot pressing under the pressure of 100 MPa at $520^\circ C$ in a vacuum atmosphere of 4×10^{-4} torr. The size of the compact obtained was $80mm \times 32mm \times 10mm$. The volume percent of these composites ranges from 0 to 30%. The ultrasonic technique (Ultrac Systems) was used for a measurement of elastic modulus. Tensile tests were carried out using an Instron machine under a cross-head speed of $1mm \text{ min}^{-1}$. Specimen machined 2mm thickness and 20mm length were used. After testing, the fracture surfaces were observed by SEM. TEM specimens were prepared from $150\mu m$ thick plate cutted with a diamond wheel cutter and were thinned to approximately $50\mu m$. Final thinning was performed using a ion milling. The ion gun parameters employed were 6 kV and 0.5 mA at 17 deg until perforation followed by 0.2 mA at 10 deg. The thin foils were observed by a JEM-2000EX.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Figure 1 shows the results for density of SiC_p/2024 Al composites as a function of SiC volume fraction after vacuum hot pressing. It was shown that the density of the composites increases with addition of SiC particles, because the density of SiC is higher than that of 2024 Al matrix. In Ni-P coated SiC particles reinforced composites, it was observed that the density of the Ni-P coated SiC particle reinforced composites is higher than that of uncoated SiC particles reinforced composites. This is due to the Ni-P

coating layer which the value of density was 8.89 g/cm³. [10] The relative density tends to be decreased as the amount of SiC volume fraction increases as shown in Figure 2. This results from that the plastic deformation of 2024 Al matrix was restricted by SiC particles during consolidation. Therefore, it was observed that the microvoid is formed between SiC particle and Al matrix as shown in Figure 3. However, we could obtain 99.7% of relative density in 30 vol% SiC_p/2024 Al composites.

Figure 4 shows the results for micro-vickers hardness of the Ni-P coated SiC particles reinforced composites and uncoated SiC particles reinforced composites. It can be found that the hardness of Ni-P coated SiC particle reinforced composites is much higher than that of uncoated SiC particle reinforced composites. This could be explained by X-ray diffraction patterns. As shown in Figure 5, it was found that the hard and brittle Ni₃P is formed in Ni-P coating layer during fabrication process at 520°C consolidation temperature. These results are agreement with the paper by J.P. Randin. [11] He reported on property of Ni-P coating layer annealed at 500°C, showing that the hardness of the Ni₃P formed in Ni-P coating layer is remarkably increased.

Generally, the elastic modulus of discontinuous ceramic reinforced composites was improved with an addition of reinforcement. The elastic modulus of the composites was shown in Figure 6. It was found that the elastic modulus is increased with an increase of SiC volume fraction. Improvement of elastic modulus results from higher elastic modulus of SiC particles over the 2024Al matrix. However, Heat treatment and Ni-P coating for SiC particles approved to be less effective in elastic modulus of composites. In order to compare with experimental data, we tried to apply the theoretically predicted equations of the elastic modulus by using Paul's equation [12], Ishai's equation [13,14] and Hashin and Shtrikman's equation [15], it was approved that the Hashin and Shtrikman's equation is better agreement with the experimental data in elastic modulus of SiC_p/Al composites.

Figure 7 shows the increase portion of specific modulus (modulus/density) of SiC_p/2024 Al composites. In 10 volume percent SiC particles, the increase portion of specific modulus of non-heat treatment SiC_p/2024 Al composites was 18% higher than that of 2024 Al. In particular, after heat treatment, the increase portion of specific modulus at 30 vol % SiC_p/2024 Al composites was about 70% higher compare with 2024 Al. This is similar to a paper reported by McDanels [16]. Consequently, the elastic properties of SiC_p/2024 Al composites are strongly affected by reinforcement volume percent.

A typical tensile strength and elongation as a function of SiC volume fraction are shown in Figure 8. The volume fraction of SiC particles was found to have a significant effect on the tensile properties of both Ni-P coated SiC_p/2024 Al and uncoated SiC_p/2024 Al composites. As the volume fraction of SiC particles increases, the tensile strength of the composites increases, but the elongation of the composites decreases. For a constant volume fraction of SiC particles, it was observed that Ni-P coated SiC particles reinforced composites exhibits much lower tensile strength and elongation compared with uncoated SiC particles reinforced composites. This is due to the formation of brittle and

hard Ni₃P within Ni-P coating layer during consolidation process. Figure 9 illustrates the fracture characteristics of (a) uncoated SiC particles reinforced composites and (b) Ni-P coated SiC particles reinforced composites. On a macroscopic scale, these composites exhibited brittle fracture mode but SEM fractograph of uncoated SiC_p reinforced composites revealed locally ductile fracture mode as shown in Figure 9 (a). From this figure, the difference could be found in the fracture surface. In uncoated SiC_p reinforced composites, the surface fractograph revealed that SiC particles exist at the base of dimple waves, formed by ductile failure of the the matrix, and SiC particles are cracked on the fracture surface as shown in Figure 9(a). These appearances indicate good bonding between SiC particles and 2024 Al matrix. However, as shown in Figure 9 (b) of the fracture surface of the Ni-P coated SiC_p reinforced composites, the fractograph revealed that failure occurs predominantly in the matrix and at the vicinity of the SiC_p/Al interface. Also, it could be found that the SiC particles are seperated from the matrix. This may be attributable to that microvoids in the coating layer rapidly grow and coalesce during tensile test because of hard and brittle Ni₃P which formed from Ni-P coating layer.

Figure 10 shows the increase portion of specific strength of SiC_p/2024 Al composites by a basis non-heat treated composites. In the 2024 Al matrix, the increase portion of specific strength was 35 % higher than that of non-heat treated composites. The increase portion of specific strength of 10 vol% SiC_p/2024 Al composites is 50 % higher than that of non-heat treated 10 vol% SiC_p/Al composites and then decreases with increasing SiC volume fraction. This is due to the volume percent decrease of heat-treated 2024 Al matrix, resulting from increase of SiC volume percent. From this result, the specific strength of SiC_p/2024 Al composites is strongly affected by the matrix properties.

4. CONCLUSIONS

The following conclusion could be obtained from this work.

1. The elastic modulus of SiC_p/2024 Al composites was found to be increased with an increase of SiC particles volume percent. Hashin and Shtrikman's theoretically equation was good agreement with the experimental data.
2. The tensile strength of SiC_p/2024 Al composites was increased after heat treatment and by adding to SiC particles but the elongation was decreased with increasing SiC volume percent.
3. After Ni-P coating for SiC particles, Ni-P coated SiC_p/2024 Al composites was largely decreased both strength and elongation.
4. The specific modulus and strength were increased with increasing SiC volume percent.

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Figure 1 The variation of density for SiC particulate volume fraction in 2024 Al and SiC_p/2024 Al composites.

Figure 2 The variation of theoretical density for SiC particulate volume fraction in 2024 Al and SiC_p/2024 Al composites.

Figure 3 Transmission electron micrograph of 30 vol% SiC_p reinforced 2024 Al composites.

Figure 4 The variation of microvickers hardness for 2024 Al and SiC_p/2024 Al composites.

Figure 5 X-ray diffraction patterns of (a) Al₂O₃, (b) Ni-P/Al₂O₃ and (c) Ni-P/Al₂O₃ annealed at 520°C.

Figure 6 Bounds on Young's modulus for 2024 Al and SiC_p/2024 Al composites.

Fig.9

Figure 7 Comparison for modulus/density ratio of 2024 Al and SiC_p/2024 Al composites. (2024 Al base line)

Figure 8 Effects of Ni-P coating for SiC particles on tensile strength and elongation of 2024 Al and SiC_p/2024 Al composites.

Figure 9 SEM fractographs of SiC_p/2024 Al composites.
 (a) SiC_p/2024 Al (b) SiC_p/Ni-P/2024 Al

Figure 10 Comparison for strength/density ratio of 2024 Al and SiC_p/2024 Al composites after heat treatment. (as fab. base line)